

Shakespeare's Unfathomable Depth in Characterisation: A Critical Lore

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Abstract

The greatness and pre-eminence of Shakespeare as a dramatist are universally recognized. He lived in an age, studied the crowd, gave them what they wanted and simply reflected their own thoughts and feelings. Critics have been trying to plunge into the unfathomable depth of Shakespeare to know him well and to trace his greatness as a literary figure. Different critics have tried to interpret the characters of Shakespeare in their own way. This has been approved by several critics that the supreme excellence of Shakespeare as a dramatist lies in his power of characterisation. In fact, Shakespeare's characters are real beings of flesh and blood. They speak like men, and not like the mouthpieces of the playwright. The secret of Shakespeare's strength comes from his unique power of close observation and sympathetic representation. His persons impress us as 'real'. In presenting his characters Shakespeare is highly tolerant; he does not take sides, and pronounces no judgment. But it is impossible to interpret Shakespeare's characters by any definite method, because they are the product of the poetic exploration of the hidden springs of human conduct and continue to appeal to his readers.

Key words: Shakespeare, great, critic, character, real.

Objectives

The objectives of the present study are

1. To take a minute look on the observations of the Shakespearean critics on Shakespeare's greatness as a dramatist.
2. To accumulate the critical observations on the unfathomable depth of Shakespeare in characterisation.
3. To find out the various facets of Shakespearean criticism on his creation of live characters.
4. To view the inner traits of Shakespearean characters both major and minor in the eye of critics.

Methodology

Love for literature is an evergreen technology to conserve environment. To accumulate the views of Shakespearean critics on the characterisation of various Shakespearean characters both major and minor attempts have been made to collect available data both primary and secondary from various sources both living and non-living, online and offline like texts and various editions of books of critics, research papers and journal articles published by the learned scholars and various websites on the topic. Paper has been prepared after careful analysis of those data accordingly.

Full Paper

*Others abide our question. Thou art free.
We ask and ask Thou smilest and art still,
Out-topping knowledge. For the loftiest hill,
Who to the stars uncrowns his majesty. Matthew
Arnold*

Indeed Shakespeare, the greatest Elizabethan poet and dramatist of England is as deep and many-sided as life and thus it requires great courage to face and understand him. One must try to

plunge into the unfathomable depth of Shakespeare to have a glimpse of the greatness of Shakespeare and his characterisation. His greatness and pre-eminence as a dramatist are universally recognized. He lived in an age, studied the crowd, gave them what they wanted and simply reflected their own thoughts and feelings. Critics have been trying to plunge into the unfathomable depth of Shakespeare to know him well and to trace his greatness as a literary figure. Different critics have tried to interpret the characters of Shakespeare in their own way. Though romantic critics hold that in him 'all came from within', practical men are of the view that in Shakespeare 'all came from without'.^(Long 1) This has been approved by several critics that the supreme excellence of Shakespeare as a dramatist lies in his power of characterisation.

The supreme excellence of Shakespeare as a dramatist lies in his power of characterisation. It is neither in diction and versification, nor in construction and the aids to construction, that the progress of the English drama incurred its deepest debt to Shakespeare. That which has given the greatest and most enduring potency to his influence upon English drama and in ever-widening circles upon the modern Western drama in general, is his own supreme gift as a dramatist, the gift of the power of characterisation. In the drawing of characters ranging over almost every type of humanity, in which the experience of succeeding generations has recognized a fit subject for the art of either the tragic or the comic dramatist, he has infinitely surpassed all the predecessors and remains absolutely without a peer.^(Bhattacharyya 108)

The greatest among the critics have, as is right and fitting, dwelt with the utmost insistence and

amplitude upon this quality of his dramatic genius. As Alexander Pope argues:

His (Shakespeare's) characters are so much Nature herself.....every single character in Shakespeare is as much an individual, as those in life itself; it is impossible to find any two alike; and such, as from their relation or affinity in any respect appear most to be twins, will upon comparison be found remarkably distinct.^(Henry 1)

Samuel Johnson in his Preface to Shakespeare opines:

This, therefore, is the praise of Shakespeare, that his drama is the mirror of life; that he who has mazed his imagination, in following the phantoms which other writers raise up before him, may here be cured of his delirious ecstasies, by reading human sentiments in human language, by scenes from which a hermit may estimate the transactions of the world, and a confessor predict the progress of the passions.^(Bloom 28)

William Richardson also asserts:

The genius of Shakespeare is unlimited. Possessing extreme sensibility, and uncommonly susceptible, he is the Proteus of the drama; he changes himself into every character, and enters easily into every condition of human nature.⁽³¹⁾

It is Samuel Taylor Coleridge who points out the problem of analysing his characters. As Coleridge comments: The characters of the dramatis personae, like those in real life, are to be inferred by the reader; they are not told to him. And it is well worth remarking that Shakespeare's characters, like those in real life, are very commonly misunderstood, and almost always understood by different persons in different ways.^(London Quarterly 12)

In comparing these four critics William Hazlitt who was among those who recognized Shakespeare's power of characterisation as his greatest excellence as a dramatic artist remarked:

The characteristic of Chaucer is intensity; of Spenser, remoteness; of Milton, elevation; of Shakespeare, everything.⁽⁶¹⁾

He is of the opinion:

...when he (Shakespeare) had conceived of character whether real or imaginary, he not only entered into all its thoughts and feelings, but seemed instantly, and as if by touching a secret spring, to be surrounded with all the same objects, 'subject of the same Skye influence' the same local, outward and unforeseen accidents which would occur in reality.^(Chambers 52)

He also observed in his book, *The Characters of Shakespeare*:

Each of his characters is as much as itself, and as absolutely independent of the rest, as well as of the author, as if they were living persons, not fictions of the mind. The poet may be said, for the time, to identify himself with the character he

wishes to represent, and to pass from one to another, like the same soul successively animating different bodies.^(Muir 45)

In fact, Shakespeare's plays are properly expressions of the passions, not descriptions of them. His characters are real beings of flesh and blood. They speak like men, and not like the mouthpieces of the author.

As a dramatist, Shakespeare is without a parallel. Even among the great classical dramatists like Aeschylus, Sophocles, and Euripides, we do not find any one so successful in characterisation. While in great Greek tragedies, men and women are often like automatons created after a set pattern to be doomed by the inexorable Fate, in Shakespeare they are living men and women, with freedom of will and judgment desperately struggling against circumstances either to win or to lose. The action is determined as much by the characters themselves as by circumstances. In Greek dramas it is the inscrutable way of Gods that moulds the human destiny; in Shakespeare it is rather our character that moulds our destiny. We gain or lose just as we deserve. This rational outlook on life as represented by Shakespeare has not lost its interest even in the age of Ibsen or Shaw.

The secret of Shakespeare's strength comes from his unique power of close observation and sympathetic representation. He knew life perhaps more than any other else; and he had a divine sympathy for life in all its forms. To him no life was mean enough, low enough but had its own virtues. His supremacy lies in this --- that he could see and understand so much of life, could pierce the heart of so many passions, without falling a prey to any aspect of life; so that we may say of him that he is universal, and we dare not say what his personality was. Every phase of feeling lay within the scope of Shakespeare's understanding and sympathy. There is no point of morals, of philosophy, of the conduct of life that he has not touched upon, no mystery of human nature that he has not penetrated. Life and death, love, wealth, poverty, the prizes of life and the way we gain them; the characters of men and the influences and forces which affect them; on all these questions Shakespeare has enriched the world with his thought.

Comparing Shakespeare's characters with those of Marlowe and Ben Jonson, Reese has observed:

Shakespeare was not interested in the man in whom the balance was entirely overthrown. Jonson was the chief among the dramatists who liked to examine the character who pursues a course of rational calculation, the man whose defects do not spring from an excess of passion but from an excess of reason. Iago was such a man. In them the will is strong, and it allows them to subdue the passions which might distract them from their chosen

purpose; but the reason is warped, and the goal ---- usually acquisition of some kind or other ---- becomes so insistently important that all impulses are killed which do not lead to it.^(Bhattacharyya 109)

In presenting his characters Shakespeare is highly tolerant; he does not take sides, and pronounces no judgment. In the quality of tolerance he excels all other authors. In this connection Saintsbury writes in *The Cambridge History of English Literature, Vol. V*:

His (Shakespeare's) severity is tempered by, and throws into relief, the quality of tolerance in which he excels every other author. This tolerance is not complaisance: justice prevents that, and sanity too. Shakespeare never winks at anything. But, as he understands everything, so, without exactly pardoning it ('that's when he's tried above'), he invariably adopts a strictly impartial attitude towards everything and everybody. In this, he stands in marked contrast to Dante, who with almost equal sanity and fully equal justice, is not merely unnecessarily inexorable, but distinctly partisan ---- not merely a hanging judge, but a hanging judge doubled with an unsparing public prosecutor..... It might be said that the extraordinary serenity and clarity of Shakespeare's mind and temper make it unnecessary for him to think whether he is fair or not. He gives the character as it is ---- the other characters --- and the reader may make what they can of it. He allows Malcolm to call Macbeth a "dead butcher" and Lady Macbeth a 'fiendlike queen', because it is what Malcolm would have done. But he does not attach these tickets to them; and you will accept the said tickets at your own risk. Another contrast which is useful is, again, that of Thackeray. The author of *Vanity Fair* and *The Newcomes* has a power of vivifying character not much inferior to Shakespeare's. But, when he has vivified his characters, he descends too much into the same arena with them; and he likes or dislikes them, as one likes or dislikes fellow creatures, not as the creator should be affected towards creations. Becky Sharp is a very fallible human creature, and Barnes Newcome is a detestable person. But Thackeray is hard on Becky; and, though he tries not to be hard on Barnes, he is. Shakespeare is never hard on any of his characters ---- not merely in the case of Lady Macbeth and Cleopatra, where there is no difficulty; but in those of Iago and Edmund, of Richard and of John, where there is. The difficulty does not exist for him. And yet he has no sneaking kindness for the bad, great person, as Milton has. The potter has made the pot as the pot ought to be and could not but be; he does not think it necessary to label it "caution" or "this is a bad pot", much less to kick it into potsherds. If it breaks itself, it must; in the shreds into which it breaks itself, in those it will lie; and "there is no more to seyn."⁽²¹²⁻³⁾

In fact, the interpretation of the characters of Shakespeare has had a history, with fluctuations, revolutions, and reactions, not determined solely by the genius or authority of particular interpreters, but reflecting general intellectual tendencies of the time. From Coleridge to Dowden this interpretation was dominated by the intellectual bias which explained kind of phenomena more readily by reason and purpose than by blind impulse and accidents, which therefore found, meaning and significance everywhere, and in particular discovered in the speech, demeanour, and fortune of every Shakespeare's character the working out of a single and coherent dramatic intention. Bradley has also, to a great extent, followed the same method. But in 1900, a pronounced reaction against this type of interpretation became apparent. Bergson had dethroned intelligence as the master faculty in man in favour of the instinctive intuition which he shares with the animal world. The prevailing psychology, from James and Wundt and M'Dougall, was preoccupied with those aspects of mentality which depend most closely upon the sense-stimuli, upon the half-unconscious and involuntary activities of instinct and habit, or upon determining or modifying social and physical conditions. It was believed that a man may be inconsistent or incoherent; he may have conflicting even contradictory moods, and yet remain indefeasible himself. Moreover, the seeming inconsistencies of an imagined character may merely betray the artist's fluctuating intention, or uncertain hand, or the capricious accesses and lulls of inspiration.

Modern psychology, by its disclosure of the phenomena of dual and multiple personality, has eased the path of those who find real inconsistency in any part of Shakespeare's characters; their inconsistency need not detract from their psychological truth. This is the stand point of Prof. Wright who recognizes with perfect clearness that our sense of a man's 'reality' not merely depends upon our being able to reduce him to a formula, but is even heightened and quickened when we find our efforts to do so futile. And Shakespeare's persons impress us as 'real' for the same reason. On the other hand, the modern realist of the more mechanical type lays hands upon every appearance of inconsistency in the characters as a sign of incongruity or incoherence in the art. Prof. Stoll and Schucking are the leaders in such critical interpretations..

There is also the 'historical' method of interpretation of character, which finds the key to Shakespeare's characterisation in the tastes, interests, and preoccupations of his audience. This method has been pursued with much labour and scholarship by Miss Lilian Winstanley in her book, *Hamlet and the Scottish Succession:*(1921)

But it is impossible to interpret Shakespeare's characters by any definite method, because they are the product of the poetic exploration of the hidden springs of human conduct. One of the distinctly original features of Shakespeare's writing is his introduction of vivid supporting characters, who are by no means two-dimensional characters. The fact that Shakespeare put so much into these characters, in comparison, say, to Marlowe, who only really has one interesting character per play, and Jonson, who deals in character types or 'humours', not fully grown individuals, makes Shakespeare's drama so much more vivid than his contemporaries.

Last but not the least, Ben Jonson's brilliant comment that Shakespeare was not of an age but of all time.⁽²⁸⁸⁾ has been the greatest tribute to Shakespeare's genius and his world of men and women. Indeed his deep insight into human nature enabled him to transcend his own time, so to speak, and to investigate problems which are still being discussed today in the light of contemporary theories. There is no iota of doubt that his immortal poetry and characters continue to appeal to his readers. Studies of Shakespeare from criticism, adaptations or rewrites have been continuing as the readers' or scholars' responses to the greatest dramatist of England offer new perspectives in the changing socio political milieu.

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